

RRING T3.3 Field notes due from each interview: Responsible Research and Innovation state-of-the-art global interviews

Contact information

Any queries in preparing for the interviews, please contact monica.racovita@anglia.ac.uk

Further details on the project more generally can be found on www.rring.eu, as well as in the accompanying Participant Information Sheet.

Field notes due from each interview

Please fill in the following online form: <https://angliaruskin.onlinesurveys.ac.uk/rring-field-notes>

The main questions you will need to reply to include:

- Justify the selection of the participants
- Did the participant struggle to make sense of any of the interview questions? (if so, did you need to provide additional information / clarification – if so, what did you say exactly?)
- What was the degree of familiarity with RRI or RRI-like dimensions?
- How concerned was the interviewee about anonymity?
- How comfortable/uncomfortable was the atmosphere for discussion?
- Were there any gender or cultural related observations that facilitated/hampered the interview?
- Any specific moments where you feel, as the interviewer, you influenced the interviewee? e.g. questions you asked, setup of the interview, framing of the whole study, interactions and responses during your discussion.
- Reflections on the structured nature of the interview?
- Any reflections or recommendations for how you would now seek to improve future interviews, based upon this interview experience?